

Addressing gender inequality: Fostering inclusive research

MINDtheGEPs Special report | Insights from the Open Forum roundtable

To take meaningful steps toward inclusive progress in research, it is imperative to challenge the traditional systems and norms that perpetuate inequality. What practical strategies can address the ongoing challenges of gender inequality in research? How can traditional evaluation methods be reformed to foster a more inclusive research environment?

On November 27 2024, MINDtheGEPs and Elsevier co-hosted an Open Forum roundtable titled "Equality in Focus: Steps Towards Inclusive Progress." This event brought together diverse stakeholders, including academics, research leaders, and advocates for gender equality, to discuss systemic barriers and explore practical strategies for fostering inclusivity in research.

The Open Forum featured insights from the *Elsevier 2024 Gender Report*, presented by Ylann Schemm, Vice President of Corporate Responsibility and Executive Director of The Elsevier Foundation. A distinguished panel of speakers shared their perspectives on how to address challenges and drive systemic change. This report synthesizes the key conclusions and recommendations from the discussion, followed by a summary of the panellists' key contributions.

Panellists:

- **Silvia Penati**, Professor of Theoretical Physics, University of Milano-Bicocca, and Chair of CoARA's TIER group.
- **Marina Calloni**, Professor of Social and Political Philosophy, and Director of the research center Against Domestic Violence (ADV), University of Milano-Bicocca.

- **Ylann Schemm**, Vice President of Corporate Responsibility and Executive Director of The Elsevier Foundation.
- **Angela Balzano**, Researcher in Sociology of Law, University of Turin, and MINDtheGEPs Trainer.

Moderator:

- **Max Voegler**, Vice President for Global Strategic Networks (DACH), Elsevier.

This report is based on the MINDtheGEPs Open Forum: *Advancing Gender Equality in Research: Insights & Synergies from the Elsevier 2024 Gender Report*. The event was co-hosted with Elsevier, a MINDtheGEPs partner organisation.

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Conclusions and recommendations

What persistent barriers hinder gender equality?

- **Systemic biases:** Challenges such as gender biases in evaluation systems, “old boys’ networks,” and underrepresentation in leadership roles limit progress. Reflection during the forum highlighted how entrenched norms perpetuate these biases, particularly privileging hyper-specialization and exclusionary structures over inclusivity.
- **Cultural and structural barriers:** Achieving sustainable progress requires shifts in both institutional culture and structural frameworks. Informal networks and systemic gatekeeping practices continue to disadvantage women, as exemplified in historical cases where recognition of women’s contributions was delayed.
- **Limitations of traditional metrics:** Conventional measures of excellence fail to capture contributions in interdisciplinary work, societal impact, and policy relevance, areas where women often excel. There is a need to redefine scientific excellence to include multi-disciplinarity and social relevance as essential measures of progress.
- **Intersectionality:** Equality efforts must address the unique challenges faced by individuals with intersecting marginalized identities.
- **Data gaps:** Reliable, nuanced data remains a cornerstone for designing and evaluating effective gender equality policies. Without comprehensive metrics, policy interventions cannot be effectively targeted.

“Achieving sustainable progress requires shifts in both institutional culture and structural frameworks.”

How can institutions promote gender equality?

- **Reform evaluation practices:** Introduce narrative CVs to enable holistic evaluations of researchers’ careers; reduce reliance on bibliometric indicators and encourage the use of double-blind peer review; and recognize interdisciplinary and societal contributions as key indicators of excellence.
- **Provide structural support:** Implement affirmative actions, such as awards for departments promoting gender equality; address biases in recruitment, mentorship, and promotion processes; and expand representation of women in editorial leadership roles. Mentorship programs and inclusive networks are critical to supporting women in navigating systemic barriers.
- **Strengthen commitments:** Adopt and implement gender action plans at institutional and national levels; allocate resources for mentorship, training, and gender equality initiatives; and foster cross-institutional collaborations to share successful practices.
- **Foster intersectional inclusion:** Include marginalized groups, such as racial minorities, LGBTQ+ individuals, and people with disabilities, in initiatives.
- **Enhance communication and engagement:** Highlight societal impact through accessible and inclusive science communication, and challenge stereotypes through diverse media platforms.

Summary of the roundtable discussion

Systemic challenges in evaluation practices

The discussion opened with an examination of how traditional evaluation systems perpetuate gender disparities. **Silvia Penati** emphasized that reliance on bibliometric indicators and rigid evaluation criteria often disadvantages women, particularly those who take career breaks for caregiving responsibilities. She argued that these frameworks fail to account for non-linear career paths.

"The current attitude in research assessment does not dig out excellence. We miss the highest quality of research because traditional criteria contain biases that distort evaluation," explained **Sylvia Penati**.

Angela Balzano highlighted the critical role of data in identifying systemic inequities, asserting that without comprehensive metrics, policy interventions cannot be effectively targeted.

"No data, no policy. Only by uncovering and understanding persistent gender inequities can we design and implement effective gender equality plans," said **Angela Balzano**.

Marina Calloni highlighted how entrenched "old boys' networks" in STEM perpetuate exclusion and delay recognition of women's contributions. These patriarchal structures reinforce systemic biases and hinder access to resources, recognition, and leadership opportunities. She referenced Barbara McClintock as an example of how groundbreaking work by women was overlooked for decades.

"These networks restrict access to resources, recognition, and opportunities, reinforcing a cycle of exclusion. The case of Nobel laureate in Genetics Barbara McClintock... is a striking example of this phenomenon," **Marina Calloni** observed.

Redefining excellence in research

The panellists agreed that traditional metrics of excellence need to evolve to better reflect the diverse contributions of researchers. **Marina Calloni** argued that redefining "scientific excellence" is essential for progress. She advocated for a broader definition that values interdisciplinarity and societal impact and critiqued traditional metrics for prioritizing hyper-specialization, which often undervalues the broader, multidimensional contributions women bring to research.

"Women's ability to integrate diverse perspectives challenges the traditional focus of 'normal' science on narrow specialization. Excellence must encompass social relevance, inclusivity, and adaptability," **Marina Calloni** emphasised.

Ylann Schemm underscored the importance of recognizing societal impact as a core measure of success, particularly for addressing global challenges such as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

"The traditional way of judging excellence is far too limited to address the challenges of our modern world. Societal impact, policy citations, and other measures of engagement should be part of how we evaluate success," **Ylann Schemm** noted.

Silvia Penati proposed the adoption of narrative CVs as a tool to contextualize researchers' contributions and provide a more holistic view of their careers and achievements.

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"If we want fairer evaluation practices, we should move beyond purely bibliometric indicators. A combination of narrative CVs and double-blind peer reviews could help reduce bias," **Silvia Penati** suggested.

Strategies for career advancement and visibility

The conversation then turned to strategies for supporting women researchers and increasing their visibility. **Angela Balzano** shared examples of affirmative action programs at the University of Turin, such as departmental awards for gender-balanced hiring practices.

"Prioritizing initiatives like hiring more women professors or creating inclusive spaces directly improves the quality of life for researchers and drives meaningful change," **Angela Balzano** remarked.

Marina Calloni emphasized the need to dismantle structural barriers in STEM through mentorship and inclusive networks. She pointed to initiatives like "Carica" as critical in empowering women to transform their academic and professional achievements into entrepreneurial and policy successes.

"Mentorship and professional networks are essential. These networks enable women to transform academic achievements into entrepreneurial and policy-oriented successes," **Marina Calloni** asserted.

Silvia Penati reflected on the increasing confidence and visibility of young women in STEM fields, describing it as a promising sign for the future.

"Young women today are not invisible. They stand up, speak out, and assert their presence in STEM fields. This cultural shift is incredibly promising," **Silvia Penati** observed.

Envisioning progress for the future

In closing, the panellists reflected on the progress made and the road ahead. **Ylann Schemm** expressed optimism about how organizations are starting to fill the female leadership pipeline, emphasizing the importance of institutional action plans in this effort.

"In a decade, I hope to see critical mass in leadership roles, reflecting the diversity we are building today. Institutional action plans and accountability will be key to sustaining this progress," **Ylann Schemm** stated.

Marina Calloni called for a vision of progress that goes beyond representation, focusing on inclusivity, interdisciplinarity, and societal impact. She argued that redefining scientific priorities and structures is critical for achieving transformative change.

"By redefining excellence, broadening the concept of innovation, and addressing structural inequalities, we can create a more inclusive and transformative scientific community. Women's contributions offer a model for a science that not only advances knowledge but also serves society as a whole," **Marina Calloni** concluded.

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